

External barrier from constructions energy to disappear of reduction economic effective solutions

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Abstract: *External barrier from constructions energy to disappear of reduction economic effective solutions today state level current from issues one is considered especially this problems solution in reaching village their houses to heating to go energy to determine and reduction is separate importance occupation it is said that*

Key words: *insulation materials, energy protector material , economic effective solutions, external barrier structures, energy loss, insulation materials, straw*

In the current era, when technology is developing, energy and to fuel was demand too increased is going This own in turn energy causes the need for rational use of resources. Each in the field updates and efficient developments everything of people requirements aimed at satisfying.

In particular, in the field of construction, the demands and wishes of consumers are the same is increasing. Accommodation Buildings are where people live and work energy efficient and economical in addition to being convenient to travel in terms of is also acceptable must be.

External structures of the building to increase the energy efficiency of the building it is necessary to cover with thermal insulation materials. It is a building or it the cost of insulation will increase. Because, market conditions

construction materials prices in particular modern heatisolation items because of the cost comes out.

Karakalpakstan Republic village in the regions of houses most of them heat isolation measures unseen simple houses organize does. Building orientation in the construction of individual houses hardly counts. In reducing energy consumption and heating houses the sun orientation effect big Buildings in designing the window and it is recommended to face the doors to the south. In addition, volumetric - history solutions also pay attention required to give.

Uzbekistan Republic in the regions construction installed heat norms QMQ 2.01.04-97* "Construction heat technique" at cited 3 ta pointer was done accordingly. A raw brick country house under study (Figure 18) rooms normal in temperature (+20 ° S) holding stand up for the costs of heating are presented in the table below (Table 6).

Table 6

No	Building heating for expendable common annual energy spending kW s/m2 year	Heat protection		
		I	II	III
		188.5	115.6	89.5
1	Gas for spent money, sum/m2 year	8,000	4 400	3 400
2	Coal for spent money, sum/m2 year	100,500	55,000	42,500
3	Firewood for spent money, sum/m2 year	107,500	58,900	45,500
4	Electric energy for spent money, amount/ m2 year	6 200	3 400	2 600

If thermal protection of the II degree is used for residential buildings, the cost of heating houses is on average 41% higher than that of a normal house decreases.

III – level heat protection if applicable houses to heating to gospital cost simple home relatively average 54% up to decrease was determined.

Costs in the use of heat insulation measures of houses himself whitewash the term account get necessary. Of this for of the house age and serviceto do term is determined. If this to the rules action if not done building energy efficiency increased with economic in terms of ineffective to the building becomes This while of families to the budget serious damage brings

Residence buildings for external the wall constructions isolationof doing technical and economic justification the following indicators according todone increase required: construction value, heating for yearly either spendingheat annual energy expenses.

Applicable remedy events population chance level to beprovide in order to in our country too cheap local of materialsuse prospects according to practical things are done is increasing.

Tashkent Architecture – construction institute scientists by done Tashkent Architecture-construction institute by state grantbased on 2017 – 18 in years M.M. Zakhidov scientific under the leadership of OT-A14-15 "The model country houses are local without increasing their prices application of energy-saving technologies based on the use of construction materials achieve" practical project completed.

Grand the project done increase according to seen experiential building twoIt is one-room, two houses consist of one dahriz. The sun is heating this house from the orientation to use too big attention directed. The sun to convert its energy into maximum heat and heat it in the winter seasonbuilding

southern to the part glazed porch placed.

of Q are referred to as grand clay h as caught building in heating 40% guaranteed energy savings possible experience showed.

Project within mean caught theoretical and experimental scientific things done increase for Tashkent province Zangota in the district in villages wide applied local from items experiential at home 2017 year from village as a result of four years of continuous experience up to now in their homes efficiency modern energy efficient of materials less didn't happen wheat straw application showed that it is possible.

This is it experience based on Karakalpakstan in the Republic is available theoretical calculation on the application of thermal insulation measures in country houses books done increased.

Applying this technology to existing rural houses in large quantities leads to energy savings. Especially among poor rural people is to be the most relevant solution. This project is available as an effective solution village in their homes 150 mm in thickness straw layer apply recommendation will be done.

In the experiment being viewed village in their homes this local material when applied heating during to disappear heat spending change the following in the table given.

Houses construction according to types	From an ordinary house to disappear heat spending kW s/ m ² years	Local heat when protection is applied (straw 150 mm), kW s/ m ² year
Raw brick	179.2	95.5
Paxa walled	178.1	101.5
Cooked brick	183	91.5

Energy protector material as simple the straw application raw brick energy consumption compared to a house without energy efficiency measures 48% gave the possibility of reduction, this result is level III according to QMQ heat protection to the results when applied near will come

Paxa walled village at home local from items when applied heat consumption decreased by 101.5 kWh/m² year and fuel consumption by 43% reduces

In Agarda, a low-rise residential building is built of adobe bricks, a wall thickness 2 (510mm) brick when 1.5 (380mm) brick to the wall in comparison heat energy consumption average to 12% decreases.

When straw is used as a heating material, the result is similar to a normal house (1.5brick) relatively almost 50% energy savings showed.

Account – books done increase – electrical, heat energy and real prices of fuels and their ability to provide heat (kcal, W hour), export price of gas, discounted local price of gas, firewood price and coal prices the following table received according to.

No	Primary fuel	Measurement unit	Received energy	Price (soum)	close for the neighbors export price (soum)
1	Natural gas	m ³	$8200 \cdot 1.163 \cdot 0.9 = 8600 \text{ Wh}$	380	2100 (\$240=1000m ³)
2	Electric energy	kWh	100%	295	10100 (\$0.24*(8.6*25%))
3	Coal	Tons	$4600 \cdot 1.163 \cdot 0.6 = 3210 \text{ W s}$	1 200 000	-
4	Firewood	Kg	$3500 \cdot 1.163 \cdot 0.4 = 1630 \text{ W s}$	600	-

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